

Mechanism of Snf5-driven transformation in human cells.

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We used whole transcriptome technologies to understand the molecular basis by which Snf5 contributes to transformation in human cells.

Cancer in humans can result from a number of sources: tumor suppressor mutation, tumor virus infection that inactivates tumor suppressors, oncogene activation like that found in lymphoma resulting from rearrangement events that fuse strong immunoglobulin promoter elements to the coding region of Myc and blood cancers resulting from translocation events. Separate from tumor suppressor inactivation or oncogene activation, a major biologic system that has been associated with transformation is the chromatin remodeling machinery that functions in ATP-mediated nucleosome remodeling: SNF5 mutation results in rhabdomyosarcoma in children, and SSX nBAF fusion oncogenes cause synovial sarcoma in adults. A fourth system whose deficiency is known to result in cancer is the mismatch repair pathway: mismatch repair germline mutation results in a cancer predisposition syndrome (Lynch syndrome), and we recently demonstrated that MSH2 is a bona fide tumor suppressor. A nuclear or transcriptional process upstream of each of the systems capable of resulting in transformation.

We studied total transcriptional output in transformed human cells following genetic depletion of SNF5 or overexpression of a wild-type SNF5 gene. Cellular processes whose function was most significantly controlled by SNF5 included oncogenic transcription factor activation (ETS family and MYC), DNA repair: BRCA1-associated DNA repair of double strand breaks, mismatch repair by MutS/MutL homologs MSH2 and PMS22L, integration events at the DNA evidenced by INTS and NBPF family genes, changes in the nuclear export pathway specific to RNA export, mutagenic processes of two variant forms: the first, a process described to function following oncogene expression and in cancer resulting from p53 loss involving cytidine deaminase *CDT1* together with ligases *HELLS* and *LIG1*, and a second oxidative damage repair process involving *UNG*, *OGG1* and *MUYTH*, a transcriptional elongation process involving *TFAP2* family members, mobilizing of the epigenetic machinery of three major sources: the *DNMT*-mediated DNA methylation system, enzymes functioning in histone demethylation and acetylation from the *KAT* and *KDM* families, and chromatin remodeling mediated *SS18L1*. The contribution of imprinting-based regulation to induction of cancer by a transformation component gene products was evidenced by significant activation of genes that function together with Xist in a recently described Xist RNP complex following genetic manipulation of Snf5, with complex composition and genomic targets that support separate functions for Xist in transformation and development.

Thus, chromatin remodeling machinery reside at a select molecular interface that defines interaction with a network of molecules that function in transformation.

Citations

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